

Pultruded Fiber Reinforced Blocked Polyurethane Composites : Static and Dynamic Mechanical Properties

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a proprietary process developed to manufacture polyurethane (PU) pultruded composites. The blocked isocyanate(NCO)-terminated PU prepolymer synthesized in this study was prepared from ϵ -caprolactam blocked the blends of toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and branched polyester. The static and mechanical properties of various fibers (glass, carbon and Kevlar 49 aramid fiber) reinforced PU composites have been studied. Results show that the mechanical properties (i.e. tensile strength, specific tensile strength, flexural strength, specific flexural strength, flexural modulus and impact strength) increase with fiber content. Kevlar fiber/PU composites possess the highest impact strength and specific tensile strength, whereas carbon fiber/PU composites show the highest tensile strength, flexural strength, specific flexural strength and flexural modulus. The glass-transition temperature (T_g) increased slightly and the damping ($\tan\delta$) peak was broaden due to fiber reinforcement. The dynamic mechanical moduli (G' , G'') of pultruded PU composites are apparently higher than those of the matrices. The moduli (G' , G'') increased the with increasing of fiber and filler content, and the damping peak becomes broad. Effect of postcuring on the degree of crosslinking, T_g and dynamic modulus will be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the pultrusion process has emerged as one of the most cost-effective processing techniques for composite materials. Pultruded composites exhibit all of the features produced by other composite processes, such as high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, electrical insulation, and dimensional stability¹⁻⁵. A number of resins have been used for pultrusion process, including the thermoset resins (unsaturated polyester, epoxy, phenolic, and methacrylate, etc.)⁶⁻¹³ and thermoplastic resins (PPS, ABS, nylon 6, etc.)¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Generally, the most suitable resin for a pultrusion process must possesses the following characters : (1). a suitable viscosity (500-2,000 cps) in the impregnation tank, (2). a long pot life in the impregnation tank, (3). a high reactivity, and (4). good wetting ability between fiber and resin¹⁸. In order to investigate the best structural application of pultruded composites, the static and dynamic mechanical properties of composites shall be studied¹⁹.

The objective of utilizing polyurethane (PU) for the pultrusion process is to take advantage of the unique properties of polyurethane including high abrasion resistance, excellent solvent and oil resistance, high tear and tensile strength, etc. Polyurethanes have been used widely in adhesion, coating, synthetic leather, construction, automobile and shoe soles, etc²⁰⁻²¹.

In this study, a blocked NCO-terminated PU prepolymer with a suitable viscosity range (500-2,000 cps) was first synthesized from its basic materials, then was reacted with chain extender, cycloaliphatic diamine (Laromin C260). The prepolymer with chain extender was used directly and polymerized in the die. This paper investigates the static mechanical properties of pultruded glass fiber, carbon fiber and Kevlar fiber, and studies the dynamic mechanical properties of pultruded glass fiber reinforced PU composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

A blocked NCO-terminated PU prepolymer synthesized from $\epsilon\epsilon$ -caprolactam blocking the blends of toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and branched polyester. The chain extender (curing agent) used was cycloaliphatic diamine (Laromin C260) and was supplied by the Shell Chemical Co., U.S.A., which has a specific gravity of 0.94-0.95, an equivalent weight with respect to active hydrogen of 60. The continuous E-glass fiber roving reinforcement used in this research was 764-NT-218 and was supplied by the PPG Co., U.S.A., which has a filament diameter of 13.1 μm , a density of 2.54 g cm^{-3} . The carbon fiber roving reinforcement used was HT-12000 and was supplied by the Toho Co., Japan, which has a filament diameter of 7.0 μm , a density of 1.77 g cm^{-3} . The continuous Kevlar fiber roving reinforcement used was K-49 and was supplied by the Dupont Co., U.S.A., which has a filament diameter of 11.9 μm , a density of 1.45 g cm^{-3} . Two fillers were used in this study, calcium carbonate (Yin Chin Co., Taiwan, R.O.C.) which has a density of 2.7 g cm^{-3} , a particle size of 350 mesh, 2.02 μm , and mica (Charles Star Enterprise Co., Taiwan, R.O.C.) which has a particle size of 325 mesh.

Apparatus

The pultrusion machine used was custom designed and consisted of a pultrusion die and multiple heating zones, as shown in Figure 1. The internal dimensions of the die were 0.210 X 1.27 X 82.0 cm (thickness X width X length). The surfaces of the stainless steel die were treated by chrome plating. A universal material testing machine was used for mechanical property tests, namely an Instron 4201 (Instron Co., U.S.A.). The impact strength testing machine utilized was a TMI-43-1 (Testing Machine Inc., U.S.A.).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Mechanical Properties

In order to investigate the effect of type and content of fiber reinforcements on the properties of pultruded PU composites, glass fiber (GF), carbon fiber (CF) and Kevlar fiber (KF) reinforced PU composites (GF/PU, CF/PU and KF/PU) with various fiber contents were fabricated at the die temperature of 180°C and the pulling rate of 40 cm/min in this study. Tensile strength, specific tensile strength, flexural strength, specific flexural strength, flexural modulus and notched Izod impact strength of composites were measured.

Tensile Strength and Specific Tensile Strength -- Figure 2 illustrates the tensile strength of pultruded glass fiber, carbon fiber and Kevlar fiber reinforced PU composites with various fiber contents. Results indicate that the tensile strength increased with fiber volume content and a linear relationship exists. CF/PU composites possess the highest tensile strength, while that of the GF/PU composite is the lowest.

The effect of fiber volume content on specific tensile strength is shown in Figure 3. The specific tensile strength of KF/PU composite is the highest, while that of GF/PU composite is the lowest among the composites studied. The specific tensile strength of KF/PU composite is higher than that of CF/PU composite, because the density of KF/PU composite is lower than that of CF/PU composite. The density of the KF/PU composite is 1.210-1.274 g cm⁻³; CF/PU composite is 1.450-1.515 g cm⁻³, and GF/PU composite is 1.892-2.010 g cm⁻³.

Flexural Strength, Flexural Modulus and Specific Flexural Strength -- The effect of fiber volume content on flexural strength and flexural modulus are shown in Figures 4 and 5. The higher the fiber volume content, the higher the flexural strength and the flexural modulus. CF/PU composite showed the highest flexural strength and flexural modulus followed by GF/PU and then KF/PU.

The effect of fiber volume content on the specific flexural strength is shown in Figure 6. It was found that the higher the fiber volume content, the higher the specific flexural strength. CF/PU shows the highest specific flexural strength followed by KF/PU and then GF/PU. The specific flexural strength of KF/PU composite is higher than that of GF/PU composite, because the density of KF/PU composite is lower than that of GF/PU composite.

Notched Izod Impact Strength -- The effect of fiber volume content on notched Izod impact strength is shown in Figure 7. The notched Izod impact strength increased linearly with fiber volume content. The Kevlar 49 fiber reinforced composites had the highest toughness, and the carbon fiber reinforced composites had the least toughness. KF/PU showed the highest notched Izod impact strength followed by GF/PU and then CF/PU.

Dynamic Mechanical Properties

The dynamic mechanical behavior of the composite is of great interest and important in structural application, and is very sensitive to the processing conditions. An unreinforced polymers and an incomplete polymerization composites still show good appearance and reasonable integrity, but the dynamic mechanical behavior would be quite different from that of a reinforced polymers and a well-polymerized composites.

Figures 8 to 9 show the dynamic mechanical spectra of pure PU and pultruded GF/PU composite in the range of -80 to 100°C. From Figure 8, one can observe that the shear storage modulus (G') increased with increasing fiber content, and the dynamic modulus of pultruded composites increased apparently as compared with the PU matrices. From Figure 9, one can observe that the glass-transition temperature (T_g) of pure PU is -52.5°C, it is noteworthy that in the presence of about 58-67 vol% glass fiber, the T_g in the composite occurred at a higher temperature (-45°C) and the damping peak becomes broad. Although the glass fiber is inert in this temperature range²², however, the dynamic mechanical properties of composite changed as compared with the matrix when the fiber are added to the PU matrix due to the effect of fiber-matrix interphase. The upshift of the glass-transition temperature, the broader damping peak and the increasing of the dynamic modulus are due to the bonding between matrix and fiber restricted the PU chain motion.

Figure 10 shows the dynamic shear storage and loss moduli (G' , G'') versus temperature of pultruded GF/PU composite at various calcium carbonate contents. From this figure, the higher the calcium carbonate, the higher the G' and G'' . Figure 11 shows the damping peak versus temperature of pultruded GF/PU composite becomes broad with increasing calcium carbonate content, however, the glass-transition temperature does not shift to higher temperatures. The dynamic moduli increase with filler due to the composite structure becomes more tightly when the filler is added.

Another important factor in determining the dynamic mechanical properties of material is the thermal history²². Thus, the original pultruded sample would may show some differences in the spectra after it was postcured, since the degree of crosslinking of composite may be enhanced. Figures 12 and 13 show the change of the dynamic mechanical properties of pultruded PU composite in the range of -80 to 100°C before and after postcured at 120°C for 60 min. From Figure 12, it can be seen that the glass-transition temperature (T_g) shifts to higher temperatures after postcured. From Figure 13, the dynamic moduli (G' , G'') increases dramatically above T_g since crosslinking shows a significant effect on the dynamic mechanical properties above T_g ¹⁹. Results showed the effect of postcuring on the shift of T_g and the increasing modulus due to the increase in degree of crosslinking. The higher degree of crosslinking make the polymer chains entangle more tightly, thus the polymer chains can not move easily. From the dynamic mechanical property studies that a glass-transition temperature (T_g) of pultruded composite around PU glass-transition occurred which indicates that the polymerization was complete at the pultrusion process²².

CONCLUSIONS

A proprietary pultrusion process has been successfully applied to prepare unidirectional fiber reinforced blocked NCO-terminated PU composites. The static mechanical properties and dynamic mechanical properties of fiber reinforced PU composites by pultrusion has been studied. The static mechanical properties (i.e. tensile strength, specific tensile strength, flexural strength, specific flexural strength, flexural modulus and impact strength) increase with fiber content. Kevlar fiber/PU composites possess the highest impact strength and specific tensile strength, whereas carbon fiber/PU composites show the highest tensile strength, flexural strength, specific flexural strength and flexural modulus.

The dynamic mechanical properties of the composites have been shown to resemble those of corresponding matrix materials. The slightly higher glass-transition temperature (T_g) and broader damping ($\tan\delta$) peak of pultruded composites were believed to be the result of fiber-introduced restraints as well as inhomogeneity as compared with the PU matrices. The dynamic moduli (G'') of pultruded PU composites are apparently higher than those of the matrices. The upshift of the glass-transition temperature, the broader damping peak and the increasing of the dynamic modulus are due to the bonding between matrix and fiber restricted the PU chain motion. The moduli (G' , G'') increased with increasing the fiber and filler content, and the damping peak becomes broad. Postcuring process can enhance the degree of crosslinking of composites. The dynamic moduli increase dramatically above T_g , and T_g shifts to higher temperatures.

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Figure 1. Flow chart of pultrusion machine.

Figure 2. Tensile Strength vs. Fiber Volume Content of Pultruded Glass Fiber (●); Carbon Fiber (■); Kevlar Fiber (▲) Reinforced PU Composites.

Figure 3. Specific Tensile Strength vs. Fiber Volume Content of Pultruded Glass Fiber (●); Carbon Fiber (■); Kevlar Fiber (▲) Reinforced PU Composites.

Figure 4. Flexural Strength vs. Fiber Volume Content of Pultruded Glass Fiber (●); Carbon Fiber (■); Kevlar Fiber (▲) Reinforced PU Composites.

Figure 5. Flexural Modulus vs. Fiber Volume Content of Pultruded Glass Fiber (●); Carbon Fiber (■); Kevlar Fiber (▲) Reinforced PU Composites.

Figure 6. Specific Flexural Strength vs. Fiber Volume Content of Pultruded Glass Fiber (●); Carbon Fiber (■); Kevlar Fiber (▲) Reinforced PU Composites.

Figure 7. Notched Izod Impact Strength vs. Fiber Volume Content of Pultruded Glass Fiber (●); Carbon Fiber (■); Kevlar Fiber (▲) Reinforced PU Composites at -50°C .

Figure 8. Dynamic Shear Storage Modulus (G') vs. Temperatures of Pultruded GF/PU Composite at Various Fiber Volume Content (%): (◇) Pure PU; (□) 58.46; (▲) 64.13; (○) 66.39.

Figure 9. Dynamic Tan Delta (damping) vs. Temperatures of Pultruded GF/PU Composite at Various Fiber Volume Content (%): (◇) Pure PU; (□) 58.46; (▲) 64.13; (○) 66.39.

Figure 10. Dynamic shear storage and loss modulus (G' , G'') vs. temperatures of pultruded GF/PU composites at various CaCO_3 contents (phr) : (\square) 0; (Δ) 20; (\circ) 40.

Figure 11. Dynamic tan delta (damping) vs. temperatures of pultruded GF/PU composite at various CaCO_3 contents (phr) : (\square) 0; (Δ) 20; (\circ) 40.

Figure 12. Dynamic tan delta (damping) versus temperature of pultruded GF/PU composite: (\square) virgin; (Δ) postcure.

Figure 13. Dynamic Shear Storage and Loss Modulus (G' , G'') vs. Temperatures of Pultruded GF/PU Composite : (\square) Virgin; (Δ) Postcure.